

Automatic License Plate Detection for Nepali Vehicles Using YOLOv11

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Abstract—Automatic License Plate Recognition (ALPR) plays a crucial role in intelligent systems, supporting applications such as traffic monitoring, toll collection, and law enforcement. Although extensive research has been conducted for countries with standardized license plate formats, limited work exists for Nepal, where license plates vary in script, style, and background. In this study, I present a deep learning-based approach for license plate detection and extraction using the latest YOLOv11, a recent variant of the YOLO object detection family. I curated a data set of 8,048 annotated vehicle images sourced from Kaggle, which were divided into training, validation, and test sets. Using YOLOv11, I trained a license plate detector and achieved 96.4% precision, 96.7% recall, and 99% map@50 in the validation set. These results demonstrate that YOLOv11 can robustly localize license plates under challenging conditions such as blurry images, occlusion, and varying lighting conditions. The detected plates can be reliably cropped for tasks such as optical character recognition (OCR) or vehicle-type classification, to identify whether the plate belongs to public, private, government, and other types of vehicles.

I. INTRODUCTION

In Nepal, the growing number of vehicles and the complex traffic conditions have created a pressing need for automated vehicle monitoring systems. A crucial component of such systems is the ability to detect and extract license plates accurately, which serves as the foundation for tasks such as vehicle identification, traffic analysis, and law enforcement [1].

Unlike standardized plates in many countries, Nepali license plates vary widely in script, color, and background. The plates may contain Devanagari, Latin, or mixed characters, and appear in challenging conditions including low lighting, blur, and occlusion. These factors make automatic license plate detection a non-trivial problem [2].

Real advancements in deep learning, particularly YOLO based object detectors, have demonstrated remarkable performance in real-time object detection tasks [3]. In this study, I used YOLOv11, the latest YOLO variant, to detect and extract license plates from Nepali vehicles. I curated a data set of 8,078 annotated images [4], split them into training, validation, and test sets. The trained model achieves 96.4% precision, 96.7% recall, and 99% map@50, demonstrating robust plate detection under varied and challenging conditions.

The main contributions of this paper are:

- Development of a YOLOv11 based license plate detection model tailored to Nepali plates.

- Experimental validation on a publicly available dataset, covering diverse scripts, colors, and environmental conditions.
- Establishing a foundation for future work in vehicle type classification or OCR for extracting license plate text.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Dataset Preparation

I utilized the publicly available Nepali Vehicle Number Plate Dataset, which contains 8,078 vehicle images along with corresponding annotations in YOLO format (bounding boxes for license plates). The images cover diverse scenarios including varying camera angles, size of the plates, and plate scripts.

The dataset was split into three subsets:

- Training set: 70% of the images (5,654 images)
- Validation set: 20% of the images (1,616 images)
- Test set: 10% of the images (808 images)

The raw dataset initially contained all images and labels in a single folder (raw_data/images and raw_data/labels). To prepare it for YOLO training, I organized the images and labels in the following folder structure:

Fig. 1. Dataset folder structure

Each image has a corresponding text file(.txt) file with normalized bounding box coordinates in YOLO format (class cx cy class w h). The split was performed using reproducible Python

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script, which shuffled the raw dataset and distributed the images across the three sets while maintaining consistency between images and labels. This organization ensures balanced distribution of samples for training and evaluation, and makes the dataset compatible with YOLO based detection pipelines.

B. Model Architecture

For license plate detection, I used YOLOv11, the latest variant of YOLO object detector family [5]. YOLOv11 offers improved feature extraction, object localization, and speed compared to previous YOLO versions [7], making it suitable for real-time applications on diverse datasets.

- Input size: 640 x 640 pixels
- Pretrained weights: yolo11.pt [6] (large model variant for better accuracy)
- Number of classes: 1 (plate)

YOLOv11 is a single-stage detector that simultaneously predicts bounding boxes and class probabilities. Its architecture is shown below:

Fig. 2. YOLOv11 architecture

The backbone extracts hierarchical features from the input image. The neck fuses multi-scale features to improve detection of objects of different sizes. The head outputs bounding box coordinates and class confidence scores.

C. Training Procedure

The training was performed using the Ultralytics YOLOv11 framework with transfer learning from pretrained weights. I initialized the model with yolo11.pt, which was pretrained on the MS COCO dataset. Fine tuning was carried out on our curated dataset of 8,048 annotated images, split into training, validation, and test subsets.

1) Training Configuration:

- Batch size: 4
- Number of epochs: 100
- Optimizer: Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD) (default)
- Loss function: YOLOv11 composite loss, consisting of bounding box regression, objectness loss, and classification loss
- Number of classes: 1 (plate)

2) *Data Augmentation:* Ultralytics YOLOv11 applies several augmentations by default, which I retained to improve robustness against lighting, scale, and orientation variations:

- Random horizontal flipping
- Random scaling and cropping
- Color jittering (hue, saturation, brightness)
- Mosaic augmentation (combining four images into one)

3) *Hardware Setup:* Training was conducted on a laptop with the following specifications:

- CPU: AMD Ryzen 7 5800H
- GPU: NVIDIA GeForce RTX 3050 Ti Laptop GPU
- Ram: 16 GB
- Framework: Pytorch 2.8 with CUDA 12.9 support

4) *Training and Evaluation Time:* On this hardware, the average epoch training time was approximately 7 minutes 50 seconds, with individual epochs ranging between 7:03 and 8:22 minutes.

Validation required significantly less time, average nearly 38 seconds per epoch with values ranging between 28 seconds and 1:12 minutes.

Table 1 summarizes the training and validation times.

Metric	Training Time	Validation time
Mean	7 min 50 sec	38 sec
Minimum	7 min 03 sec	28 sec
Maximum	8 min 22 sec	1 min 12 sec

TABLE I

AVERAGE TRAINING AND EVALUATION TIMES PER EPOCH

5) Checkpoints and early stopping:

- The best model weights were automatically saved based on validation mAP@50.
- Training stopped after 100 epochs since no significant overfitting was observed.

This configuration with the small batch size allowed the model to achieve stable convergence despite the hardware limitations of a 4 GB GPU.

D. Evaluation Metrics

The performance of the license plate detector was evaluated using standard object detection metrics [7]:

- Precision (P): Measures the proportion of correctly predicted license plates among all predicted plates.
- Recall (R): Measures the proportion of correctly detected license plates among all ground truth values.
- Mean Average Precision (mAP): Evaluates both precision and recall across different thresholds of Intersection-over-Union (IoU).
 - mAP@50: Average precision at an IoU threshold of 0.5, a widely used metric for object detection tasks.

- mAP@50-95: Average precision computed over multiple IoU thresholds ranging from 0.5 to 0.95 with a step size of 0.05, providing stricter evaluation.

The YOLOv11 framework computes these metrics automatically during training and validation, allowing us to track model performance across epochs.

III. RESULTS

A. Dataset Results

The YOLOv11 automatically generated a visualization of the bounding box distribution in the dataset [8]. This shows the variation in plate sizes, aspect ratios, and locations across images, confirming that the dataset covers a wide range of scenarios.

Fig. 3. Distribution of license plate bounding boxes in the dataset

B. Training Curves

During training, YOLOv11 automatically generated values for box loss, classification loss (cls), distribution focal loss (DFL) and performance metrics (precision, recall, mAP) [9]. I plotted the box_loss, cls_loss, dfl_loss values and the graph shows the model converged stably and somewhat plateaued at the end as shown below:

C. Detection Performance

After training YOLOv11 for 100 epochs on the curated dataset, the model achieved the following performance on the validation set:

- Precision (P): 96.4%
- Recall (R): 96.7%

Fig. 4. Training loss plot

- mAP@50: 99%
- mAP@50-95: 93.2%

These results indicate that model was highly effective in detecting license plates under diverse conditions. The high precision demonstrates that most detected bounding boxes correspond to true license plates, while the high recall indicates that very few license plates were missed.

The performance metrics plot is shown below which shows the convergence of our model to the truth:

Fig. 5. Training metrics plot

To further evaluate the detector, I analyzed the precision-recall (PR) curve [10]. The PR curve demonstrates a high area under the curve, confirming that the model maintains both high precision and recall across different confidence thresholds.

Fig. 6. Precision-Recall curve

Fig. 7. F1-score curve

Fig. 9. Validation batch 1 predictions

Fig. 10. Validation batch 2 labels

Fig. 11. Validation batch 2 predictions

D. Qualitative Results

The sample image detections are from the validation sets. The model successfully localizes the license plates in images with high probability values.

Fig. 8. Validation batch 1 labels

IV. DISCUSSION

A. Model Performance

- YOLOv11 achieved high precision (96.4%) and recall (96.7%), showing robust license plate detection across Nepali vehicles.
- The high mAP@50 (99%) and mAP@50-95 (93.2%) indicate that the model accurately localizes plates with minimal false positives or missed detections.
- Loss curves demonstrated stable convergence, suggesting that the large YOLOv11 model was suitable for this dataset despite its moderate size.

B. Dataset Considerations

- The dataset contains variations in plate sizes, aspect ratios, colors, and occlusion, which contributes to a realistic evaluation scenario.

C. Limitations

- The study focuses only on plate detection and extraction, not character recognition. OCR and vehicle type classification remain future work.

- The dataset is limited to images captured from a specific set of cameras and regions in Nepal (Bagmati Province), which may affect generalization.

D. Potential Applications

- Cropped license plate images can be used for future OCR tasks to read plate numbers.
- Plate detection can be combined with color-based vehicle-type classification for private, commercial, government, etc. vehicles.
- The method can be used for traffic monitoring, parking management, and other intelligent transportation systems in Nepal [11].

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

A. Conclusion

In this study, I developed a deep learning based approach for license plate detection and extraction in Nepali number plates using YOLOv11. I curated a dataset of 8,048 annotated vehicle images and split them into training, validation, and test sets. The trained YOLOv11 model achieved 96.4% precision, 96.7% recall, and 99% map@50, demonstrating robust performance under challenging real-world image conditions.

The results confirmed that YOLOv11 is highly effective for localizing Nepali license plates and producing reliable cropped plate images. These cropped plates can serve as an input for future OCR systems or vehicle classification pipelines, enabling intelligent transportation applications in Nepal.

B. Future Work

While this study focuses on plate detection, several avenues remain for extending this research:

- 1) *Optical Character Recognition (OCR)*: Developing a CRNN-or transformer based OCR system to read the characters on Nepali plates, including mixed Devanagari and Latin scripts.
- 2) *Vehicle type classification*: Using plate colors and extracted plate images to classify vehicles as private, commercial, government, diplomatic etc.
- 3) *Integration with Traffic Systems*: Combining speed detection and license plate detection to automatically identify vehicle information and issue traffic fines to over speeding vehicles.

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